

Triterpenoids. Part XIV. Studies on the Constitution of Barringtonol C - a New Triterpenoid Sapogenin from *Barringtonia Acutangula* Gaertn

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A new triterpenoid sapogenin, $C_{30}H_{50}O_3$, named barringtonol C, has been isolated from the fruits of *Barringtonia acutangula* Gaertn. Selenium dioxide oxidation of its penta-acetate furnishes a diene, showing triple ultraviolet absorption maxima, characteristic of $\Delta^{11-12,13-18}$ dienes of the β -amyrin series. The presence of an α -glycol and one 1,3-diol system has been shown. Possible constitution of the sapogenin has been discussed.

In our previous communication¹ the isolation of a number of new sapogenins from the fruits of *Barringtonia acutangula* Gaertn was reported. The constitution of one of the sapogenols, barringtonol D has been established as $3\beta,22\beta,28$ -trihydroxy-16 $\alpha,21$ α -oxido-olean-12-ene². The present communication describes our studies on the constitution of another sapogenol, named barringtonol C, isolated from the same source.

Barringtonol C, $C_{30}H_{50}O_3$, formed a penta-acetate and a pentabenzoylate, thus showing presence of five hydroxyl groups. The hindered double bond in barringtonol C resisted catalytic hydrogenation under normal conditions. The penta-acetate and the pentabenzoylate, each, consumed nearly one mole of perbenzoic acid at a rate typical of triterpenes of the β -amyrin group having a double bond at 12-13 position. Barringtonol C consumed one mole of periodic acid, thus showing presence of an α -glycol system in it³.

Selenium dioxide oxidation of the penta-acetate of barringtonol C furnished a diene, m. p. 244-48°, which showed triple ultraviolet absorption maxima at 243, 252, and 261 $m\mu$, typical of the $\Delta^{11-12,13-18}$ dienes^{3,4} of the β -amyrin series. An α - β -unsaturated ketone, $C_{30}H_{48}O_{11}$, m. p. 316-20° (11-keto compound, λ_{max} 245 $m\mu$; log ϵ , 4.1), is obtained when the penta-acetate is oxidised with chromium trioxide in boiling acetic acid. The corresponding 11-keto compounds⁵⁻⁸, obtained from other triterpenes of the β -amyrin group, show UV absorption maxima at about 247 $m\mu$. In the case of barringtonol D, the maxima was, however, at 241 $m\mu$ due to presence of the oxide linkage. Moreover, barringtonol C

1. Barua *et al.*, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1961, **50**, 937.
2. Chakraborti and Barua, *Exper.*, 1962, **18**, 60.
3. Barton and Brooks, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 257.
4. Ruzicka *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1939, **22**, 767.
5. Barua and Raman, *Tetrahedron*, 1959, **7**, 21.
6. Noller, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **66**, 1269.
7. Djerassi *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1956, **78**, 5698.
8. Cainelli *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1957, **40**, 2390.

penta-acetate furnished a 12-keto derivative^{9,10}, $C_{40}H_{60}O_{11}$, m.p. 244-46°, on treatment with perhydrol-acetic acid. It did not exhibit any colour with tetranitromethane. On the basis of the above observations, it is concluded that most probably barringtogenol C is a triterpene belonging to the β -amyrin group, having a double bond at the 12-13 position.

Presence of one primary hydroxyl group was shown by the formation of a monotrityl derivative, $C_{49}H_{64}O_3$, m.p. 254-61°. Pyrolysis of barringtogenol C with copper-bronze afforded formaldehyde (cf. hederagenin¹¹ and arjunolic acid¹²) which was identified as its dimedone derivative. Barringtogenol C, when treated with pyridine and benzoyl chloride at 0°, furnished a mixture of pentabenzoate and a tribenzoate, $C_{51}H_{68}O_8$, m.p. 271-74°, which could be separated by chromatography over a column of acid-washed alumina. The tribenzoate did not react with periodic acid. Acetylation of barringtogenol C at room temperature, however, furnished the penta-acetate. Further work on the constitution of barringtogenol C is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

Selenium Dioxide Oxidation of the Penta-acetate.—Barringtogenol C penta-acetate (0.5 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (20 ml) and refluxed with freshly prepared selenium dioxide (0.5 g.) for 4 hours. The product was worked up in the usual way and chromatographed over acid-washed alumina when a small amount of a crystalline material, m. p. 238-43°, was obtained. This on repeated crystallisation from methanol furnished rectangular plates, m. p. 244-48°, in extremely poor yield. It showed characteristic UV-absorption maxima for a conjugated diene (*vide supra*).

Oxidation of the Penta-acetate with CrO₃.—To a boiling solution of barringtogenol C penta-acetate (200 mg.) in glacial acetic acid was added CrO₃ (200 mg.) in acetic acid (85%, 10 ml). After refluxing for 2 hours, the mixture was diluted with water and worked up in the usual way. The product was purified by chromatography over acid-washed alumina and crystallised from methanol as colorless needles, m. p. 316-20°. (Found: C, 67.06; H, 8.23. $C_{40}H_{56}O_{11}$ requires C, 67.21; H, 8.17%.)

12-Keto Derivative.—To a solution of barringtogenol C penta-acetate (0.5 g.) in glacial acetic acid (15 ml) 30% H_2O_2 (5 ml) was added dropwise and the mixture heated on a water bath for 4 hours. It was then poured on crushed ice. The crude product was chromatographed over acid-washed alumina and crystallised from benzene-petroleum (b. p. 60-80°) mixture as colorless needles, m. p. 244-46°, [α]_D+7.5° ($CHCl_3$). (Found: C, 66.9; H, 8.85. $C_{40}H_{60}O_{11}$ requires C, 67.01; H, 8.43%.)

Trityl Derivative of Barringtogenol C.—A solution of barringtogenol C (2 g.) and triphenylchloromethane (8 g.) in dry dioxane-pyridine mixture (1:1, 160 ml) was heated

9. Ruzicka and Cohen, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1937, 20, 804.

10. Picard *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 1045.

11. Tsuda and Kitagawa, *Ber.*, 1938, 71, 1604.

12. King *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 3995.

on a steam bath for 8 hours and left overnight. It was poured on crushed ice; the product on chromatography over acid-washed alumina gave a fraction which crystallised from chloroform-methanol mixture, m.p. 254-61°. (Found: C, 79.86; H, 8.68. $C_{49}H_{64}O_3$ requires C, 80.28; H, 8.8%).

Pyrolysis of Barringtogenol C with Copper-bronze.—An intimate mixture of barringtogenol C (0.5 g.) and finely powdered copper-bronze (1g.) was heated in a metal bath at 350-60° for 1 hour and a slow stream of nitrogen was passed through the reaction vessel to carry over the evolved gases which were passed into a saturated aqueous dimedone solution. After 1 hour the precipitate was collected and crystallised from aqueous methanol, m. p. 188-89° alone or mixed with formaldehyde dimedone derivative.

Partial Benzoylation of Barringtogenol C.—To a solution of barringtogenol C (2 g.) in dry pyridine (40 ml) was added benzoyl chloride (2 ml) at 0° and left for 14 hours at the same temperature. The crude reaction product was chromatographed over acid-washed alumina. Elution with light petroleum-benzene mixture (2:1) furnished the pentabenzoate, m. p. 314-17° (mixed m.p. with barringtogenol C pentabenzoate remained undepressed). Benzene: petroleum (2:1) eluate provided a colorless glassy product which crystallised from chloroform-methanol mixture, m.p. 271-74°. (Found: C, 76.01; H, 7.88. $C_{51}H_{62}O_8$ requires C, 76.25; H, 7.78%).

Acetylation of Barringtogenol C at room temperature.—To a solution of barringtogenol C (500 mg.) in pyridine (10 ml) was added acetic anhydride (5 ml) and left overnight at room temperature. It was worked up in the usual way and the product after crystallisation from methanol had m. p. 222-24°. It did not depress the m. p. of barringtogenol C penta-acetate, when admixed.

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